

Upper Extremity Motor Symptomsâ€™ Severity Estimation with Ecologically Valid Data Arising from Smartphone Touchscreen

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Objective:

The study aims to provide an objective passive monitoring tool for the fine-motor impairment as reflected by the clinical evaluation of UPDRS Part III Single item scores, by analyzing touchscreen typing data of healthy and early Parkinson's Disease patients.

Background:

Objective high frequency data arising from everyday devices can be used to monitor habits of individuals that can be linked to health status, and further used for monitoring and early detection of motor impairment. Exploiting the sensing capabilities of smartphones, these data could be deployed to perform large-scale human studies. Aiming towards early detection of Parkinson's Disease, touchscreen data were collected passively from two clinically examined cohorts via a mobile app (iPrognosis) and were analyzed in order to find the ability of app-derived indices capturing the severity of bradykinesia and rigidity.

Design/Methods:

The study was designed hereby by employing a cohort of 33 (demographically-matched 18/15 PD/healthy controls) that typed multiple text excerpts in-the-clinic. By analyzing the timing sequences (press and release actions) of the keystroke typing activity and employing machine learning, two indices were created: RSi and BSi for Rigidity and Bradykinesia Severity index, respectively. A separate cohort, comprising of 15/8 PD/Healthy controls, used the iPrognosis keyboard as the default input method for their routine typing activities on their smartphones. In order to aggregate the produced indices in a subject-level, median of the total produced indices was calculated and was compared to the clinical labels.

Results:

Correlation of the predicted indices with the UPDRS Part III single item scores achieved 0.71, 0.64 and 0.54 with the alternate finger tapping test, bradykinesia and rigidity of the subjects, respectively. Moreover, the diagnostic performance achieved was 0.9 area under the receiver operating characteristics curve.

Conclusions:

Touchscreen based indices hereby show promising performance on detecting the severity of fine-motor impairment even when data is captured in-the-wild.